

Impact of Project Management Practices on the Performance of the Core Fund Management System in the Public Sector: A Case of National Social Security Fund (NSSF) Head Quarters, Tanzania

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of project management practices on the performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at Tanzania's National Social Security Fund (NSSF). Adopting a cross-sectional design, the research targeted 47 Information Communication Technology (ICT) professionals directly involved in the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) project and a statistically determined sample of 186 out of 346 system users, selected using Yamane's formula to ensure representativeness. Data was collected through structured, self-administered questionnaires featuring closed-ended questions and Likert-scale items. This method enabled efficient data gathering and ensured respondent anonymity, which encouraged honest feedback. The analysis employed descriptive statistics and Spearman's Rank Correlation to explore the relationship between adherence to project management practices and Core Fund Management System (CFMS) performance. The results revealed a significant positive correlation ($\rho = 0.336$, $p = 0.021$), indicating that adherence to structured project management practices enhances system performance. Key findings suggest that while practices during the initiation, planning, execution, and closing phases were generally adhered to, there were areas for improvement in stakeholder engagement and issue management. The study concludes that consistent project management positively influences Core Fund Management System (CFMS) performance and recommends enhanced stakeholder engagement, increased training in project management methodologies, and routine evaluation of practices. Future research should explore the long-term impact of improved stakeholder engagement on system performance and project success.

Keywords: *Project management practices, Core Fund Management System, ICT projects, Public Sector, System Performance.*

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Introduction

The adoption of application software development projects in the public sector is vital for enhancing service delivery, operational

efficiency and governance (Kweka & Ndbilema, 2018). Public organizations worldwide are increasingly integrating ICT and digital solutions to meet these demands

(Rumanyika & Mashenene, 2014). According to the United Nations E-Government Survey (2020), digital government strategies are essential for advancing public service delivery and achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as they improve transparency, efficiency, and citizen engagement. However, software development within public organizations faces unique challenges, including resource limitations, regulatory requirements and a diverse set of stakeholders, emphasizing the need for effective project management (PMI, 2017).

Effective project management practices are critical for ICT project success, especially within the Tanzanian public sector, where ICT adoption is viewed as a key factor in achieving Vision 2025's goals for sustainable development (Kweka & Ndibalema, 2018). Studies show that tailored project management methods can mitigate risks, improve collaboration and ensure project objectives are met on time and within budget (Schwalbe, 2015). Approaches like Agile have proven particularly beneficial in software development by allowing flexibility and adaptability to changing project requirements (Serrador & Pinto, 2015). Project management also improves resource allocation, communication and adherence to industry standards, reducing risks and enhancing the quality and timely delivery of software solutions (Cajic, 2023; Kagan, 2023).

Tanzania's National Social Security Fund (NSSF) leverages ICT to enhance service delivery, with the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) being a cornerstone application that supports critical functions like member and employer registration, inspections, contribution management, benefit and pension payments (NSSF, 2023). Overseen by the e-Government Agency, the CFMS serves as a sophisticated tool for executing essential NSSF operations. However, the effectiveness of project management practices during CFMS's development and implementation remains underexplored, leaving potential gaps in understanding its impact on system performance and user satisfaction. The CFMS case study thus provides a valuable opportunity to evaluate the role of project management practices in public

sector ICT projects and their influence on system reliability and service quality.

Despite significant investments in ICT, NSSF's CFMS has encountered issues like delays, inefficiencies and usability problems, potentially due to inconsistent project management practices (Ngowi, 2019). Research suggests that challenges like inadequate planning, weak stakeholder engagement and limited risk management have led to system underperformance in public sector ICT projects (Alotaibi, 2019; Ramesh et al., 2018). Such problems often result in unmet project objectives, with users of CFMS experiencing reduced satisfaction and efficiency. Existing literature on project management in ICT emphasizes the importance of thorough initiation, planning, execution and monitoring to prevent such issues (Mtolera, 2022).

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between project management practices and the performance of CFMS at NSSF to bridge the research gap in public sector ICT project management. By analyzing adherence to project management practices among ICT professionals and assessing CFMS's current performance, this research clarifies how these practices impact operational outcomes and user satisfaction.

Literature Review

Application software is designed to help end-users perform specific tasks across personal, educational, or business domains (Quickbase, 2024). In this study, the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) is the focal application software, designed to support the National Social Security Fund's (NSSF) essential functions. These include managing employer and member registration, conducting routine inspections, handling the collection and distribution of contributions, and facilitating the payment of benefits and pensions to members. Key performance indicators for CFMS include timely task execution, user-friendliness, reliability, operational cost efficiency and user satisfaction (AVI Network, 2024).

A project is a unique endeavor that organizes resources to achieve specific objectives within set constraints of time, cost, and environment (Alotaibi, 2019). Project management, as defined by the Association for Project Management (2024), applies structured processes, methods and skills to achieve objectives within specific timelines, scope and budget. The Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK) Guide, developed by the Project Management Institute, offers best practices tailored to different projects, including application software development and organizes project management practices into five stages: initiating, planning, executing, monitoring and controlling and closing (Roseke, 2020; Visual Paradigm, 2023). Each stage has a distinct role, from setting objectives and developing plans to managing resources, tracking performance and ensuring project closure with stakeholder satisfaction. These practices are critical for achieving project goals effectively.

Theoretical Framework

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), explains how perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) impact technology acceptance and usage. PU is the belief that a technology will enhance job performance, while PEOU pertains to the effort required to use it. When users perceive a system as both beneficial and easy to use, they are more likely to adopt it, increasing overall system effectiveness (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). While TAM is widely accepted for its empirical validity, it has faced criticism for being overly simplistic, as it does not account for social, organizational, or experiential factors that might influence technology acceptance (Lee, 2009; Bagozzi, 2007). Nonetheless, TAM remains foundational due to its adaptability and the potential to incorporate additional variables such as user satisfaction and social influence for a more comprehensive understanding of technology adoption (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008; Venkatesh et al., 2012).

In this study, TAM is applied to examine adherence to project management practices and the performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF. By analyzing the

perceptions of both ICT professionals and end users regarding CFMS's usefulness and ease of use, the study explores how these factors influence system adoption, adherence to project goals, and operational outcomes. ICT professionals' views on the CFMS impact its development and alignment with project management standards, while end users' acceptance determines how effectively the system supports daily operations, influencing efficiency and operational success. Applying TAM enables to assess whether higher perceived usefulness and ease of use correlate with better project management adherence and enhanced CFMS performance, thus providing insights into technology adoption and potential areas for improvement in system effectiveness and user engagement (Venkatesh et al., 2012).

Empirical Literature Review

Existing research shows a consistent relationship between project management practices and project success across different sectors and regions, though results vary. Ramesh et al. (2018) found a positive link between human resource management and project success in India's Warangal region, while Alotaibi (2019) reported a strong association between project management practices and success in large contracting firms in Saudi Arabia. Similarly, Hussain et al. (2022) noted that projects incorporating project management tools saw better outcomes in ten countries, and Varajao et al. (2022) found that adherence to ISO 21500/PMBOK processes contributed significantly to Information System project success internationally. In Kenya, Kaluai (2020) also observed that effective project practices, including stakeholder involvement and structured risk management, improved project performance in economic empowerment programs, while Laikipia County's construction sector benefitted from strong risk management frameworks.

Contrastingly, some studies report negative associations between project management practices and project outcomes. For example, Naserizaker (2020) found that, in Iran, project management practices related to cost and budget control did not correlate positively with success,

suggesting complexities within the local project environment. Likewise, Mtolera (2022) noted a negative relationship between project management practices and project performance at TANESCO in Tanzania, highlighting challenges specific to regulatory and team competency frameworks in the public utility sector.

Despite these insights, there is a gap in understanding how project management practices influence application software projects specifically. Most studies, including Haron et al. (2017) in construction and Lanyoh (2019) in banking, have focused on different industries, leaving application software development largely unexplored. While Varajao et al. (2022) addressed project management in Information Systems, there remains a need for comprehensive studies that utilize the PMBOK model to assess software projects' success. Furthermore, Tanzanian public sector research on project management practices is limited, apart from Mtolera's (2022) study on TANESCO.

To address these gaps, this study focuses on the impact of PMBOK-guided project management practices on the success of application software projects within Tanzania's public sector, specifically the National Social Security Fund (NSSF). This research aims to provide insights into the relationship between adherence to PMBOK practices and successful software project outcomes, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of project management's role in software development in public institutions.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study assesses the relationship between Project Management Practices (independent variable) and the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) performance (dependent variable) at the National Social Security Fund (NSSF). Project Management Practices involve the adherence of ICT professionals at NSSF to established project management standards and methods, ensuring successful planning, execution and completion of the CFMS. On the dependent side, CFMS performance encompasses aspects like

efficiency, reliability, user satisfaction and alignment with organizational goals. The mediating variable is the relationship between adherence to Project Management Practices and system performance, representing how this adherence impacts CFMS performance. Influencing factors, such as project complexity, organizational support, and suitability of the project management approach, also play a role in this relationship, providing insights into how these dynamics affect system outcomes.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Synthesis of literature review

Methodology

The study examines the relationship between project management practices and the performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at the National Social Security Fund (NSSF) in Tanzania, adopting a positivist research paradigm to explore quantifiable impacts. Positivism was selected due to its focus on empirical evidence and objective measurement, making it ideal for investigating cause-and-effect relationships in a structured way (Bhandari, 2020). The central research question—"What is the relationship between project management practices and the performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at the National Social Security Fund (NSSF) in Tanzania?"—aligns with positivist ideals, aiming to demonstrate a clear link between adherence to project management protocols and measurable outcomes within the public organization context. This approach allows the researcher to remain unbiased and use numerical data to substantiate findings,

providing valuable insights into how project management practices may enhance system performance.

The research design chosen was cross-sectional, gathering data from a range of respondents within a limited timeframe due to constraints related to the Master's program at the Tanzania Institute of Project Management (Thomas, 2020). The cross-sectional approach captures a snapshot of the current practices and outcomes related to the CFMS at NSSF, offering a timely reflection on how the system's development aligns with best practices in project management. This design enables the examination of specific management practices, such as planning, execution, and risk management, in connection to the system's performance. To achieve this, structured questionnaires were distributed to 47 ICT professionals, who contributed to CFMS development, and a sample of 186 out of 346 CFMS users, calculated using Yamane's formula to yield a statistically sound representation without requiring responses from all users (Etikan et al., 2016).

Data collection involved structured, self-administered questionnaires containing closed-ended questions and Likert scale items to gauge adherence to project management practices and assess CFMS performance indicators like user satisfaction and system functionality. This method was chosen for its efficiency in gathering large amounts of quantitative data and ensuring respondent anonymity, encouraging honest responses (Mark & Janina, 2018). The survey focused on collecting views from two groups: ICT professionals who directly influence the system's development and application software users who experience the system's outcomes daily. This dual focus allows for a well-rounded understanding of project management practices and their operational impact from both technical and user perspectives.

Rigorous data management procedures ensured the quality and reliability of collected data, beginning with cleaning to remove incomplete responses and detect outliers. Data was then coded, with Likert scale responses converted into numerical values, simplifying statistical analysis. Responses were grouped

thematically—project management adherence and system performance—allowing for composite scores that facilitated comparison and correlation analyses. Descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation provided a summary of adherence and performance levels, and Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient was employed to examine the relationship between project management practices and CFMS performance. The correlation analysis indicated whether adherence positively or negatively influenced system effectiveness, categorized by established criteria (Turney, 2022).

The study adhered strictly to ethical guidelines outlined by the Tanzania Institute of Project Management. Informed consent was obtained from participants, who were informed of the research purpose before data collection. To maintain privacy, respondents were not required to provide identifying information, and data was handled with strict confidentiality protocols to protect participant anonymity. Ethical practices included permission from relevant authorities, reinforcing the study's commitment to transparency and respect for participant rights. These ethical measures ensured the credibility and reliability of the research process, supporting unbiased data collection and interpretation in assessing the effects of project management on public-sector software performance.

Findings of the Study

Response Rate

The response rates for the study's two main respondent groups at the National Social Security Fund (NSSF)—ICT professionals and CFMS users—are shown in Table 1.

The study at the National Social Security Fund (NSSF) in Dar es Salaam targeted 47 ICT professionals involved in developing the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) and 186 CFMS users across various departments, distributing a total of 233 questionnaires. All targeted respondents participated, achieving a 100% response rate from both ICT professionals and CFMS users, as shown in Table 5.1. This exceptional response rate

strengthens the representativeness of the data, providing a robust basis for analysis and interpretation. The full engagement of

respondents also suggests a high level of interest in the study, enhancing the validity of its findings (Babbie, 2020).

Table 1. Response Rate of Respondents

Respondent Group	Targeted Sample	Responses Received	Response Rate (%)
ICT Professionals	47	47	100
CFMS Users	186	186	100
Total	233	233	100

Source: Field Data (2024)

Demographic Information of the Respondents

Table 2 summarizes the demographic characteristics of ICT professionals at NSSF Head Offices, covering gender distribution,

educational qualifications, and years of work experience. This data provides a comprehensive view of the team's composition, which is relevant for assessing workforce diversity and expertise.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of ICT Professionals at NSSF Head Offices

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Sex	Female	17	36.2
	Male	30	63.8
	Total	47	100
Educational Qualifications	Diploma	10	21.3
	Bachelor's Degree	29	61.7
	Master's Degree	8	17
	Total	47	100
Experience	1-3 years	16	34
	4-10 years	23	48.9
	11-20 years	6	12.8
	Above 20 years	2	4.3
	Total	47	100

Source: Field Data (2024)

The demographic analysis of ICT professionals at NSSF Head Offices highlights three key aspects: gender, educational qualifications, and years of work experience. Among the 47 respondents, 63.8% are males and 36.2% are females, indicating a gender imbalance. Regarding educational qualifications, 61.7% hold a bachelor's degree, 21.3% have a diploma, and 17% possess a master's degree, showcasing a workforce with a strong foundation in undergraduate education and a small portion with advanced qualifications. In terms of experience, 34% of respondents have 1-3 years of experience, 48.9% have 4-10 years, 12.8% have 11-20 years, and only 4.3% have more than

20 years, indicating that most ICT professionals are early to mid-career.

These findings reflect typical demographic trends in ICT. The gender disparity, where men outnumber women, aligns with global trends of male dominance in ICT roles, which can limit diversity and creativity within teams (UNESCO, 2021). Educationally, while the high proportion of bachelor's degree holders brings essential theoretical knowledge, the relatively low number of professionals with master's degrees suggests potential for growth in specialized areas such as data analytics and project management (Kerzner, 2017). Additionally, the predominance of early to mid-career professionals offers opportunities

for fresh perspectives but underscores the need for mentoring by senior staff. Establishing mentorship and advanced training initiatives could help bridge the experience gap and enhance the department's capacity to manage critical ICT projects (PMI, 2021).

Table 3 summarizes the demographic characteristics of CFMS users at the NSSF Head Offices, including sex, educational qualifications, and work experience. This distribution provides insights into the diverse backgrounds of system users, which may influence system interaction and performance.

Table 3. Demographic Characteristics of CFMS Users at the NSSF

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Sex	Male	75	40.3
	Female	111	59.7
Education Qualifications	Diploma	59	31.7
	Bachelor's Degree	97	52.2
	Master's Degree	30	16.1
Work Experience	1-3 years	60	32.3
	4-10 years	91	48.9
	11-20 years	27	14.5
	Above 20 years	8	4.3
Total Respondents		186	100

Source: Field Data (2024)

The demographic data on the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) users at the NSSF Head Offices reveal a varied group in terms of gender, education, and work experience. Out of 186 respondents, 59.7% are females, while 40.3% are males, indicating a higher representation of female users. Regarding educational qualifications, the majority hold bachelor's degrees (52.2%), followed by diploma holders (31.7%) and a smaller group with master's degrees (16.1%). In terms of work experience, 48.9% of users have 4 to 10 years of experience, with a notable 32.3% in the 1 to 3-year range, 14.5% with 11 to 20 years, and only 4.3% exceeding 20 years of experience. This distribution highlights a blend of early, mid, and late-career professionals within the CFMS user base.

These findings suggest a balanced gender representation, which can enhance the system's inclusivity and help cater to diverse user perspectives, aligning with recommendations for ICT system inclusivity (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The predominance of bachelor's degree holders indicates a user group with foundational technical skills, while diploma and master's degree holders bring practical experience and

specialized knowledge, respectively (Kerzner, 2017). The range in work experience suggests that most users are relatively seasoned (1–10 years), with a smaller but important segment of senior professionals (over 10 years) who may provide mentorship and guidance, supporting effective knowledge transfer and continuity in system usage (Cox, 2020; Allen et al., 2017). Such demographic diversity in gender, education, and experience contributes to a well-rounded workforce capable of supporting CFMS operational goals and adapting to evolving organizational demands (UNESCO, 2021).

The Adherence to Project Management Practices Among the ICT Professionals of NSSF During the Development of the Core Fund Management System

This study assessed how closely ICT professionals at NSSF followed Project Management Practices during the development of the Core Fund Management System. ICT professionals at NSSF's Head Offices were asked several questions about their adherence to these practices, rating each statement on a scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree" to indicate their level of agreement.

Adherence to Key Project Management Practices During the Initiation Phase

Table 4 presents data on adherence to key project management practices during the initiation phase of the Core Fund Management

System (CFMS) development project at NSSF. This table summarizes responses on activities such as requirements gathering, stakeholder engagement, and feasibility study assessments, all of which are critical for establishing a solid project foundation.

Table 4. Adherence to Project Management Practice at the Initiation Phase

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Requirements gathering and project objectives were clearly defined before the start of the Core Fund Management System development.	47	4.4	0.712	Agree
Stakeholders were adequately identified and engaged during the initiation phase of the Core Fund Management System project.	47	3.94	1.223	Agree
The feasibility study conducted during the initiation phase provided realistic expectations and constraints for the Core Fund Management System development.	47	4.36	0.705	Agree

Source: Field Data (2024)

The findings indicate that during the initiation phase of the Core Fund Management System project at NSSF, project management practices were largely adhered to, as evidenced by high levels of agreement on clearly defined requirements (mean = 4.4, SD = 0.712) and an effective feasibility study setting realistic project expectations (mean = 4.36, SD = 0.705). However, stakeholder engagement scored lower with more variability (mean = 3.94, SD = 1.223), suggesting that while engagement was generally adequate, there were challenges in achieving full

consensus, highlighting an area for potential improvement.

Adherence to Project Management Practices at the Planning Phase

Table 5 summarizes ICT professionals' responses at NSSF regarding key project management practices during the Planning Phase of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) project. The table covers aspects such as project planning, risk management, and team readiness.

Table 5. Adherence to Project Management Practices in the Planning Phase

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
A detailed project plan, including timelines, milestones, and resource allocation, was developed for the Core Fund Management System project	47	3.57	1.193	Agree
Risk management strategies and contingency plans were established and documented during the planning phase of the Core Fund Management System project.	47	3.83	0.916	Agree
The project team was adequately trained and prepared to execute the planned activities during the planning phase of the Core Fund Management System project.	47	4.11	0.814	Agree

Source: Field Data (2024)

The findings from Table 5 reveal a moderate level of agreement (mean = 3.57, SD = 1.193) among ICT professionals that a comprehensive

project plan was created for the Core Fund Management System, although the higher standard deviation indicates some variability in

perceptions about the plan's detail. There was stronger consensus on risk management, with a mean score of 3.83 (SD = 0.916), suggesting that strategies were adequately documented. Furthermore, team training and preparation received high agreement (mean = 4.11, SD = 0.814), highlighting a well-prepared team ready to implement the project. Overall, the results indicate general satisfaction with planning practices, though some professionals perceived inconsistencies in project planning comprehensiveness.

Adherence to Project Management Practices at the Execution Phase

Table 6 presents ICT professionals' feedback on adherence to project management practices during the Execution Phase of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) project at NSSF. The table covers key areas such as task implementation, monitoring, and change management.

Table 6. Adherence to Project Management Practices at the Execution Phase

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Activities and tasks were implemented according to the defined project plan during the execution phase of the Core Fund Management System development.	47	4.11	0.814	Agree
Progress and performance were regularly monitored and reported during the execution phase of the Core Fund Management System project.	47	3.94	0.919	Agree
Changes and deviations from the project plan were managed through formal change control processes during the execution phase of the Core Fund Management System project.	47	4.3	0.587	Agree

Source: Field Data (2024)

The findings from Table 6 indicate strong adherence to project management practices during the execution phase of the Core Fund Management System at NSSF. ICT professionals generally agreed that activities were implemented as per the project plan (mean = 4.11, SD = 0.814), progress was regularly monitored (mean = 3.94, SD = 0.919), and changes were managed through formal change control processes (mean = 4.3, SD = 0.587). These results reflect effective execution practices, with structured change management, consistent monitoring, and adherence to planned activities, all of which are

essential for maintaining control and achieving successful project outcomes.

Adherence to Project Management Practices at the Monitoring and Evaluation Phase

Table 7 summarizes ICT professionals' views on adherence to project management practices during the Monitoring and Evaluation Phase of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) project. It includes feedback on monitoring, issue management, and change control processes.

Table 7. Adherence to Project Management Practice at the Monitoring and Evaluation Phase

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Progress and performance metrics were effectively monitored and reported during the development of the Core Fund Management System	47	4.09	0.855	Agree
Issues and deviations from the project plan were promptly identified and addressed during the Monitoring and Controlling phase of the Core Fund Management System project.	47	2.68	1.086	Somehow Agree

Changes to project scope or objectives were managed through formal change control processes during the Monitoring and Controlling phase of the Core Fund Management System project.	47	3.96	0.556	Agree
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Source: Field Data (2024)

The findings from Table 7 show that ICT professionals generally agreed that progress and performance metrics were effectively monitored and reported during the Monitoring and Evaluation Phase of the Core Fund Management System (mean = 4.09, SD = 0.855). They also agreed that changes to project scope or objectives were managed through formal change control processes (mean = 3.96, SD = 0.556). However, responses indicated only moderate agreement regarding the prompt identification and resolution of project issues (mean = 2.68, SD = 1.086), suggesting inconsistencies in issue management. Overall, while monitoring and

change management were effective, there is an opportunity to improve the timeliness of issue identification and resolution.

Adherence to Project Management Practices at the Closing Phase

Table 8 summarizes ICT professionals' perspectives on adherence to project management practices during the Closing Phase of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) project at NSSF. It highlights activities such as documenting lessons learned, conducting formal reviews, and completing closure tasks.

Table 8. Adherence to Project Management Practice at the Closing Phase

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Lessons learned and best practices from the Core Fund Management System project were documented and shared within the organization.	47	4.09	0.59	Agree
The Core Fund Management System project was formally reviewed to assess its achievements and identify areas for improvement in future projects.	47	4.02	0.649	Agree
Necessary project closure activities, such as finalizing project documentation and archiving project files, were completed effectively for the Core Fund Management System project.	47	3.74	0.743	Agree

Source: Field Data (2024)

The findings in Table 8 indicate a strong adherence to project management practices during the closing phase of the Core Fund Management System project at NSSF. ICT professionals agreed that lessons learned were effectively documented and shared (mean = 4.09, SD = 0.59), the project underwent a formal review to assess achievements and guide future improvements (mean = 4.02, SD = 0.649), and necessary closure activities were completed (mean = 3.74, SD = 0.743). Overall, these practices support formal project closure, organizational learning, and continuous

improvement within NSSF, helping ensure project knowledge is retained and future projects benefit from identified best practices and areas for enhancement.

Performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF

The performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF, as indicated by user ratings, reveals several key insights. The table 9 below summarizes the findings based on user feedback.

Table 9. Performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF

Performance Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
The Core Fund Management System is user-friendly and easy to navigate.	186	3.51	1.04	Agree
The Core Fund Management System effectively meets the operational needs of NSSF.	186	3.80	0.942	Agree
The Core Fund Management System improves efficiency in managing the Fund's collected contributions payments by streamlining various processes.	186	3.30	1.435	Somehow Agree
The Core Fund Management System provides accurate and reliable data for decision-making.	186	3.39	1.121	Somehow Agree
I am satisfied with the performance of the Core Fund Management System at NSSF.	186	3.83	0.681	Agree

Source: Field Data (2024)

Users generally find the CFMS user-friendly, with a mean score of 3.51 (SD = 1.04). The system is effective in meeting operational needs, achieving a mean score of 3.8 (SD = 0.942). However, feedback regarding its efficiency in managing contribution payments was mixed, reflected in a mean score of 3.3 (SD = 1.435). The reliability of the system in providing accurate data for decision-making received a mean score of 3.39 (SD = 1.121), indicating moderate agreement but variability in user experiences. Overall satisfaction with the CFMS was high, with a mean score of 3.83 (SD =

0.681), demonstrating that it meets user expectations and contributes positively to their work.

Relationship between Adherence to Project Management Practices and the Performance of the Core Fund Management System

The analysis of the relationship between adherence to Project Management Practices and the performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF is presented in the Table 10 The results indicate a significant positive correlation between these two variables.

Table 10. Correlation Matrix

			Adherence to Project Management practices	Performance of Core Fund Management System
Spearman's rho	Adherence to Project management practices	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.336*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.021
		N	47	186
	Performance of Core Fund Management System	Correlation Coefficient	.336*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.021	.
		N	47	186

Note: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The study reveals a significant positive relationship between adherence to Project Management Practices and the performance of the CFMS, as indicated by a Spearman's rho correlation coefficient of 0.336 (p = 0.021). This suggests that better adherence to these practices is associated with improved system performance, with the correlation being

statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Although the correlation is moderate, it confirms that adherence to Project Management Practices positively influences CFMS performance. The findings align with the Project Management Institute's perspective that structured processes enhance efficiency and effectiveness in system management.

Discussion

The findings for the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) development at NSSF highlights several key insights regarding adherence to Project Management Practices across different phases.

During the Initiation Phase, the study indicates a strong foundation for project success, characterized by clearly defined requirements and objectives. This clarity is crucial, as it minimizes risks associated with scope creep and project delays, supporting effective resource allocation and stakeholder satisfaction (Alotaibi, 2019). While there was a general agreement on stakeholder engagement, some variability suggests that not all stakeholder perspectives were adequately considered, potentially leading to unresolved issues later in the project. This emphasizes the need for a more inclusive approach to stakeholder engagement to ensure all relevant voices are acknowledged (Lanyoh, 2019). The feasibility study conducted was recognized as effective in setting realistic expectations, highlighting its importance in assessing project viability early on (Bagchi et al., 2015). Overall, the Initiation Phase was well-managed, but improvements in stakeholder engagement practices are necessary.

In the Planning Phase, adherence to project management practices was positively perceived, although responses varied regarding the thoroughness of the project plan. A well-structured project plan is vital for aligning team members with objectives and timelines (Kerzner, 2017). However, the variability in responses indicates potential misalignments in understanding the plan's details, suggesting that clearer communication is needed. On risk management, the study found a strong consensus that strategies were established, yet there is room for improving communication about these strategies to enhance team readiness in addressing risks (PMI, 2021). Training for the project team was also rated positively, affirming that adequate preparation is essential for effective project execution, which can significantly influence overall project outcomes (Gido & Clements, 2018).

The Execution Phase showcased strong adherence to project management practices, with a notable commitment to implementing activities according to the project plan. This reflects effective project management that aligns with defined objectives and timelines, which is crucial for achieving project success (Kerzner, 2017). Regular monitoring and reporting of progress were generally practiced, but the variability in responses indicates a need for standardized processes to ensure all team members are informed and able to take corrective actions promptly (PMI, 2021). Change management processes were also rated positively, highlighting the effectiveness of formal procedures in managing project alterations and maintaining alignment with strategic goals (Turner, 2014). This phase demonstrated a solid adherence to practices necessary for controlling the project and achieving successful outcomes.

In the Monitoring and Evaluation Phase, findings revealed strong adherence to monitoring practices, suggesting effective oversight of project activities and performance. Consistent monitoring facilitates timely decision-making and helps manage project risks, crucial for maintaining project momentum (PMI, 2021). However, the lower agreement regarding the prompt identification and resolution of issues points to challenges in issue management, indicating a need for improved uniformity across teams in addressing emerging problems (Kerzner, 2017). The study also affirmed that changes to the project scope were managed through formal processes, reinforcing the importance of structured change management in maintaining project integrity (Turner, 2014).

Finally, the Closing Phase demonstrated a strong commitment to documenting lessons learned and conducting formal project reviews, essential for organizational learning and continuous improvement (Schwalbe, 2020). The practice of sharing lessons learned enhances the organization's knowledge base and informs future projects, fostering a culture of accountability (Turner, 2016). Although essential project closure activities were generally completed effectively, the adherence to closure

protocols is vital for ensuring that all project deliverables are finalized and that relevant information is archived for future reference (Larson & Gray, 2021). Overall, these practices in the Closing Phase contribute to a seamless transition from project completion to operational integration, ensuring that valuable insights are retained for subsequent initiatives.

The findings on the performance of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF reveals a generally positive reception among users, highlighting strengths in usability and operational effectiveness. Users perceive the system as user-friendly, which is critical for fostering high adoption rates and minimizing frustration (Smith & Jones, 2024). Moreover, the system's ability to meet operational needs reinforces its role in supporting daily functions at NSSF, aligning with findings that underscore perceived usefulness as a significant predictor of user satisfaction (Brown, Davis, & Miller, 2023). However, mixed feedback regarding the system's efficiency in managing contribution payments suggests areas needing enhancement, particularly in streamlining processes like employer and member registration (Nguyen & Thompson, 2024). The variability in users' experiences regarding data accuracy also points to potential improvements that could enhance the system's value as a decision-support tool (Garcia & Lopez, 2024). Overall, while the CFMS meets several key user needs effectively, continued efforts to refine usability and efficiency are essential for sustained user satisfaction and operational excellence.

The analysis of the relationship between adherence to Project Management Practices and the performance of the CFMS at NSSF indicates a significant positive correlation, with a Spearman's rho correlation coefficient of 0.336 ($p = 0.021$). This suggests that enhanced adherence to structured project management methodologies contributes to better system performance, confirming insights from the Project Management Institute that effective processes improve efficiency and effectiveness in system management (PMI, 2021). As organizations face evolving technological and operational landscapes, the application of robust project management practices becomes critical

for adaptability and alignment with strategic goals (Kerzner, 2017). These findings underscore the importance of maintaining comprehensive project management frameworks and investment in training for ICT professionals to promote adherence to these methodologies. Furthermore, the need for regular evaluations of project management practices is emphasized, particularly in areas identified with moderate adherence, to identify opportunities for improvement and achieve superior system performance.

Conclusions

The study concluded that the development of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF exhibited strong adherence to Project Management Practices across various phases. The Initiation Phase established a solid foundation with well-defined requirements, though variability in stakeholder engagement highlighted the need for a more inclusive approach. In the Planning Phase, while the project plan received positive feedback, clearer communication was essential for aligning team understanding. The Execution Phase demonstrated effective alignment with objectives, but standardized processes for monitoring and reporting were necessary to ensure timely corrective actions.

In the Monitoring and Evaluation Phase, oversight of project activities was effective, yet challenges in issue management indicated a need for greater consistency across teams. The Closing Phase emphasized the importance of documenting lessons learned and conducting formal project reviews, contributing to organizational learning and smoother operational transitions.

Regarding the performance of the CFMS, users generally viewed it positively, particularly appreciating its user-friendliness and ability to meet operational needs. However, mixed feedback on efficiency in managing contributions pointed to areas for improvement, especially in registration processes and data accuracy. Notably, a significant positive correlation was found between adherence to Project Management Practices and system performance, underscoring the importance of

ongoing training for ICT professionals and regular evaluations of project management practices to adapt to evolving organizational needs.

Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness of the Core Fund Management System (CFMS) at NSSF, it is recommended to implement a more inclusive stakeholder engagement process throughout project phases. This involves regular consultations with all relevant stakeholders to incorporate diverse perspectives, which can help identify potential issues early and increase user satisfaction.

Investing in training programs for ICT professionals and project team members on project management methodologies is also crucial. By equipping staff with advanced project management skills, NSSF can promote adherence to best practices, leading to improved system performance and better adaptation to operational challenges.

Finally, prioritizing the ongoing evaluation and refinement of project management practices is essential. Special focus should be placed on areas with moderate adherence, like risk management and issue resolution, to identify improvement opportunities. Regular reviews of project management frameworks will help ensure that the CFMS remains aligned with NSSF's evolving needs.

Recommendation for Future Studies

For future studies, it is recommended to explore the long-term impacts of enhanced stakeholder engagement on the performance and user satisfaction of the Core Fund Management System. Investigating how different engagement strategies influence project outcomes could provide valuable insights for refining practices in public organizations.

Additionally, further research could examine the relationship between specific project management methodologies and system performance metrics over time. By analyzing various approaches and their effectiveness in diverse contexts, future studies could contribute to developing a more tailored project

management framework for organizations like NSSF.

References

- Alotaibi, A. B. (2019). *Project Management: The Implication of Project Management Practices on Project Success in Saudi Arabia*. Doctor of Philosophy Thesis, University of Portsmouth, Department of Operations and Systems Management.
- AVI Network. (2024). *Application Performance Definition*. Retrieved on February 25, 2024, from <https://avinetworks.com/glossary/application-performance/#:~:text=Application%20performance%20indicates%20how%20the,of%20service%20to%20end%2Dusers>.
- Babbie, E. (2020). *The Practice of Social Research* (15th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Bagchi, K., Kirs, P., Udo, G., & Cervený, R. (2015). Characteristics and determinants of insourced and offshored projects: A comparative analysis. *Journal of World Business*, 50(1), 108–121.
- Bagozzi, R. P. (2007). On the use of structural equation models in experimental research: A note on the issues of causality. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 34(2), 258–267.
- Bhandari, P. (2020, June 12). *What Is Quantitative Research? | Definition, Uses & Methods*. Retrieved on February 28, 2024, from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>
- Brown, A., Davis, J., & Miller, K. (2023). Perceived usefulness and user satisfaction in management systems. *Journal of Information Systems*, 41(1), 45–60.
- Cajic, D. (2023, October 30). *How Important is Project Management in Software Development?* Retrieved on February 15, 2024, from <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-important-project-management-software-development-dino-cajic-wrvgc>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.

- Garcia, M., & Lopez, R. (2024). Data quality and decision support in management systems. *Decision Support Systems*, 67(4), 112-130.
- Gido, J., & Clements, J. (2018). *Successful Project Management*. Cengage Learning.
- Hussain, S. B., Uddin, M. K., Uddin, S. M., & Ali, M. F. (2022). The Impact of Project Management Practices on Project Success. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 9(22).
- Kagan, J. (2023, November 21). *Importance of Project Management in Today's Business Landscape: Delivering Our Thoughts and Findings on the Future of Project Management!* Retrieved on February 16, 2024, from https://niftypm.com/blog/importance-of-project-management/#3_Improved_communication_and_collaboration
- Kaluai, F. K. (2020). *Project Management Practices and Performance of Projects under the Women and Girls Economic Empowerment Program in Kiambu and Nairobi City Counties, Kenya*. Master's Dissertation, Kenyatta University, Department of Business Administration.
- Kerzner, H. (2017). *Project Management: A Systems Approach to Planning, Scheduling, and Controlling*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Kweka, K. H., & Ndibalema, P. (2018). Constraints Hindering Adoption of ICT in Government Secondary Schools in Tanzania: The Case of Hanang District. *International Journal of Educational Technology and Learning*, 4(2), 46-57.
- Lanyoh, E. R. (2019). *Project Management Practices: A Comparative Study of Three Selected Banks in Ghana*. Master's Thesis, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology.
- Larson, E. W., & Gray, C. F. (2021). *Project Management: The Managerial Process*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Lee, Y. (2009). The role of social influence in the acceptance of technology: A systematic review. *Journal of Technology Management & Innovation*, 4(1), 95-110.
- Mtolera, J. J. (2022). *Impact of implementation of project management practices on success of project a case of TANESCO-Kilimanjaro northern zone*. Dissertation for Master of Project Planning and Management, Institute of Accountancy Arusha.
- Naserizaker, N. (2020). Implementation Of Project Management in Iranian Projects to Complete High-Quality Projects in A Timely Manner. *Scientific Research and Development Russian Journal of Project Management*.
- Ngowi, H. (2019). An assessment of the effectiveness of the Core Fund Management System in public financial management in Tanzania. *Public Administration Review*, 79(4), 534-546.
- Nguyen, T., & Thompson, R. (2024). Efficiency and user satisfaction in management systems. *Journal of Operations Management*, 29(3), 98-115.
- NSSF. (2023). *National Social Security Fund*. Retrieved February 10, 2024, from <https://www.nssf.go.tz/>
- PMI. (2017). *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK® Guide)*. Project Management Institute.
- PMI. (2021). *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK Guide) (7th ed.)*. Project Management Institute.
- Quickbase. (2024). Retrieved on February 25, 2024, from <https://www.quickbase.com/articles/application-software-basics>
- Ramesh, E., Babu, D. R., & Rao, R. P. (2018). The Impact of Project Management in Achieving Project Success- Empirical Study. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 9(13), 237-247.
- Rumanyika, J., & Mashenene, R. G. (2014). Business Constraints and Potential Growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Tanzania: A Review. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(32), 72-79.
- Schwalbe, K. (2015). *Information Technology Project Management*. Cengage Learning.
- Serrador, P., & Pinto, J. K. (2015). Agile work? — A quantitative analysis of agile project success. *International Journal of Project Management*, 33(5), 1040-1051.

Thomas, L. (2020, May 8). *Cross-Sectional Study | Definition, Uses & Examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/cross-sectional-study/#:~:text=A%20cross-sectional%20study%20is,observe%20variables%20without%20influencing%20them>

Turner, J. R. (2014). *Handbook of Project-Based Management: Leading Strategic Change in Organizations*. McGraw-Hill.

Turner, J. R. (2016). *Gower Handbook of Project Management*. Gower Publishing, Ltd.

Turney, S. (2022, May 13). *Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) | Guide & Examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/statistics/pearson-correlation-coefficient/>

UNESCO. (2021). *Closing Gender Gaps in STEM: Global Report on ICT and Gender Diversity*. Paris: UNESCO.

United Nations. (2020, July). *United Nations E-Government Survey 2020: Digital Government in the Decade of Action for Sustainable Development (With addendum on COVID-19 Response)*. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from <https://www.un-ilibrary.org/content/books/9789210051453#:~:text=The%20Survey%20assesses%20global%20and,of%20the%20Sustainable%20Development%20Goals>.

Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186-204.

Venkatesh, V., Thong, J. Y., & Xu, X. (2012). Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: Extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 36(1), 157-178.